

Technogenic and Geochemical Diagnostics of Soils Distributed on the Territory of the "Kremikovtsi" Metallurgical Plant

Mariela Stoykova

Institute of Soil Science, Agrotechnologies and Plant Protection "Nikola Poushkarov", 7 Shosse Bankya str., 1331 Sofia, Bulgaria

Corresponding Author: Mariela Stoykova

e-mail: m.stoykova@issapp-pushkarov.org

Received: 12 December 2022

Accepted: 1 February 2023

Abstract

The content of Rubidium, Strontium, Cesium and Barium in soils with a metamorphic and poorly developed profile, subjected to active technogenic pollution from the activity of the former Kremikovtsi metallurgical plant, was analyzed. Six profiles were included in the study - 5 of Technosols from the plant territory and one external control profile of Rhodic Cambisol. Metal content was determined by the LA-ICP-MS method, with data obtained simultaneously with data for over 50 chemical elements. According to the results obtained, the average content of Rb is (in $\mu\text{g/g}$) 206.10, of Sr - 156.05, of Cs - 12.97 and of Ba - 1876.80, with the values for Barium, Rubidium and Cesium exceeding the average world reference values by 4, 3 and 2.5 times respectively and those of Strontium are slightly below them. The contents of the four metals are genetically determined and naturally geochemical inherited from the high initial contents in the soil-forming proluvial sediments. Contamination has contributed to a very large accumulation of the heavy alkaline earth metals Ba and Sr in all alkalized spolic/carbonate surface horizons of Technosols, where they are present as sparingly soluble sulfates, carbonates and phases adsorbed by iron and manganese oxides. A statistically significant positive correlation was determined between Ba and Pb, based entirely on the technogenic effect, in which part of the accumulated lead was adsorbed by sparingly soluble secondary sulfates and carbonates of the alkaline earth metals and especially Barium. The alkali metals in these soils migrate down the soil profile. In the uncontaminated Rhodic Cambisol, their behavior is similar - they migrate downward and concentrate in the carbonate B_{ck} horizon. This observation allows considering the concentration of the heavy alkaline earth metals Ba and Sr in the surface soil horizons as a sign of irreversible or difficult to reverse technogenic soil degradation manifested in the formation of secondary salts of heavy metals, gradual alkalization of the environment and loss of soil colloids.

Keywords: contaminated soils, Technosols, alkalization, barium, strontium, rubidium, cesium

Introduction

The content of Rubidium, Strontium, Cesium and Barium in soils is not of interest to traditional agricultural science because these are not indispensable elements for living organisms (Perelman, 1989; Kabata-Pendias, 2011).

The soil profiles, object of the present study, are from the territory of the former metallurgical plant "Kremikovtsi", near the capital of Bulgaria, the city of Sofia, which developed heavy metallurgical activity for over 50 years. Due to its strategic location, numerous studies have historically been conducted on the impact on soils and waters in the region. According to them, both due to diffuse (aerosol, dust), and due to point and mechanical pollution, soils are contaminated with heavy metals and metalloids, mainly Pb and As, and have a pronounced alkaline reaction (Faitondzhiev et al., 2000, Shulin et al., 2004, Stoykova, 2021, etc.). Faitondzhiev et al. (2000) noted that carbonate content was particularly high in soils near the smelter and these values had only increased within the previous large-scale survey.

In the present study, the results for the contents of Rb, Cs, Sr and Ba were obtained simultaneously with the data for more than 50 chemical elements. After a number of statistical calculations, this made it possible to define the region's characteristic geochemical soil associations of elements formed under the influence of natural or technogenic local soil-forming factors.

In this extensive database, the obtained naturally elevated values of the four metals, their characteristic chemical nature, as well as the historically accumulated knowledge of pollution problems in the area, predetermine the purpose of the research presented in this article - to study the behavior of the four elements in context of the long-term technogenic pollution with pollutants of diverse composition and in conditions of their naturally elevated background norms.

Rubidium, Cesium, Strontium and Barium are representatives of the most active metals from the groups of alkali and alkaline earth metals from the s-block of the periodic table. As heavier representatives of these groups, they possess the peculiarities in the atomic structure - greater nuclear charge and the presence of d- and f- electrons in the inner electronic layers, which determines similarities with their pedogenic counterparts, dividing them into two separate geochemical associations - Na, Ca, Sr on the one hand and K, Rb, Cs, Ba on the other hand (Stefanova, 2005; Fersman, 1953). This division has a geochemical meaning, from which arise differences in the behavior of the discussed metals in many directions. The monovalent alkali metals Rb and Cs are easily susceptible to weathering and migration in the soil environment, where they migrate as weakly hydrated ions whose fixation is mainly controlled by clay soil minerals. Similar to potassium, they accumulate to some extent in the humus horizon of soils (Orlov et al., 2005; Kabata-Pendias, 2011; Nakao et al., 2003). Strontium is readily released by weathering of primary minerals, is moderately mobile, migrates through stable hydrated ions, and binds tightly to clay soil minerals and SOM. In carbonate soils similar to those investigated in this project, strontianite (SrCO_3) can precipitate, which lowers its mobility (Kabata-Pendias, 2011, Burger et al., 2019). The mobility of Barium in soil is also affected by its pH, and in carbonate-alkaline environments it precipitates as sulfates and carbonates or binds tightly to clay minerals, but in acidic environments it could leach out of the soil profile, similar to calcium. This metal is characterized by a strong affinity for adsorption by manganese oxides and, accordingly, its concentration in manganese concretions, a product of a variable oxidation-reduction soil regime. In this adsorption, Barium displaces the remaining alkaline earth metals and a number of other transition metals from their positions (Jaritz, 2004; Kabata-Pendias, 2011).

Because of similarities in atomic structure with their pedogenic and biogenic counterparts potassium and calcium, the four metals have biochemical pathways for accumulation in living

organisms. According to Perelman (1989), according to his calculated coefficient of biological uptake (A_x), reflecting the biophilicity of chemical elements, Strontium is characterized by strong accumulation, Barium is characterized by medium uptake, and Cesium is characterized by low uptake in living organisms. In the investigated contaminated soils, the biogenic factor has minimal impact, which is an additional feature of these soils.

Materials and Methods

A total of 15 profiles were included in the study - 11 contaminated and four control profiles, on which all standard soil tests were performed. From them, six basic ones were selected for additional chemical and mineralogical studies. The baseline profiles include 5 Technosols from the site of the Kremikovtsi plant and one external control profile of Rhodic Cambisol in a northwesterly direction from the plant. The soil profiles are made with a great depth (up to 400 cm), in order to evaluate simultaneously the natural and the techogenic factors affecting the ecological status of the entire region. They are placed next to workshops with different activities and pollution, in order to make it possible to carry out comparative man-made diagnostics of the soils according to the type of pollutant.

Geologically, the entire studied area is located on an extensive Pliocene proluvial plume, generated from fragments and redeposited products of rocks from the adjacent mountain slope, carried by the surface flowing waters and accumulated in a number of proluvial cones located along the entire length of the northern fence strip of the Sofia hollow. Representative for the area are Rhodic-Chromic Cambisols). The specific studied territory from the plume is mainly fed by two proluvial cones at the foot of the Sofia Stara Planina (provisionally called western and eastern) and has a very specific petrographic composition and heterogeneous age of the rocks. In the western direction, the soil-forming rocks are enriched mainly with debris and redeposited products with a syene composition originating from the Buhovo-Seslavtsi potassic-alkaline magmatic pluton (Profile 3 and Profile 13c - Cambisols). In the eastern direction, the soil-forming rocks are enriched with ore mineralization from the Bukhov uranium deposit (Profile 6, Ex. 7, Ex. 8 and Ex. 11 - Regosols) (Angelov et al., 2008, Dyulgerov, 2005, Kalaidzhiev, 1993). Additionally, soil-forming sediments everywhere contain redeposited products of Paleozoic metamorphosed siltstones, argillites, lydrites, etc. and carbonate and argillaceous-carbonate Triassic and Jurassic rocks, all of which also make up the adjacent mountainsides (Figure 1).

The content of Rb, Cs, Sr and Ba was determined by mass spectrometry using the LA-ICP-MS method, with data obtained simultaneously with data for over 50 chemical elements. The soils were also examined for all the main soil indicators - mechanical composition, CEC, pH, SOM, etc.

Results are interpreted based on calculated parameters such as average content, minimum - maximum value; Brave's linear correlation coefficient (r) with statistical significance in intervals ($-1 \div -0.5$) and ($0.5 \div 1$), calculated by the formula $|r| \geq 3 \cdot \sigma_r$, where $\sigma_r = (1 - r^2)/\sqrt{n}$ and "n" is the number of pairs in the correlation (Rollinson, 1993); concentration coefficient (CC), calculated as the ratio between the content of the element in the specific horizon of the profile (K_e) relative to its content in the lowest horizon of the same profile (K_c) K_e/K_c (Fersman, 1953; Stefanova, 2005).

Morphologically, the studied soils are reddish in color (50% of all samples are 5 YR), with high fragmentation, partially naturally covered. Cambisols are powerful, have well-formed genetic horizons, and Regosols have a layered profile structure. Soil-forming sediments are observed everywhere - alternating layers of gravel, sand and clay. Vegetation in contaminated profiles is sparse or absent.

Based on the determined toxic levels of a number of pollutants in them, both types of contaminated soils have a modified taxonomy and are now classified as Technosols (IUSS Working Group WRB, 2015; Stoykova, 2021; Teoharov, 2019).

Figure 1. Right: Geological map of the region. In **pink color** - Buhovo-Seslavtzi pluton; **green and orange** - Paleozoic rocks; **blue and violet** - Triassic and Jurassic sediment; **yellow** - neogene; **gray** - Quaternary (according to Angelov et al., 2008, M 1:50000). Left: Geographical location of the studied profiles

Results and Discussion

According to the obtained results, the average content of Rb is (in $\mu\text{g/g}$) 206.10, of Sr - 156.05, of Cs - 12.97 and of Ba - 1876.80, with the values for Barium, Rubidium and Cesium exceeding the average world reference values by 4, 3 and 2.5 times respectively, and those of Strontium are slightly below them (Table 1; Table 2). The contents of the four metals are genetically determined by the high initial contents in the soil-forming proluvial sediments, mainly composed of redeposited monzonites, syenites, lamprophyres, etc., part of the composition of the Buhovo-Seslavtzi potassium-alkaline pluton, and for the high local Barium geochemical background there is a share and Bukhov Uranium Ore Field - both geological sites forming wide areas of the adjacent mountain slopes (Angelov et al., 2008; Dyulgerov, 2005; Kalaydzhiev, 1993). According to Dyulgerov (2005), the geochemical characterization of the Buhovo-Seslavtzi magma body determines that elements with large ionic radii (LILE) such as Rb, Cs, Sr and Ba are of high and very high contents, with average values in $\mu\text{g/g}$ for Rb - 341.3, Cs - 16.1, Sr - 591 and Ba - 1716 (min 1149 - max 2284). In this primary geochemical association are elements with a high ionic potential (HFSE) such as Th, U, Zr, Hf, Nb, etc., also distinguished by very high contents in the source igneous rocks, according to the data of the same author. In the soils, a product of redeposited proluvial rocks with this initial composition in our study, we observed that three of the studied metals - Rb, Cs and Sr - preserved a statistically significant correlation with the elements of the primary geochemical association. The correlation indicators between Rb, Cs and Sr on the one hand and K, Na, P, Th (Table 4), Zr, Nb, Hf, Sn, etc. are significant. (Stoykova, 2021). These are all rock-forming and accessory mineral building elements specific to potassic-alkaline intrusives (Kamenov, 2003). In support of this thesis are the obtained data on the maximum contents of Rb, Cs and Sr in the composition of Technosols (cambic) (Profile 3), whose soil-forming materials are of the youngest age.

Table 1. Rubidium, Strontium, Caesium and Barium content, some important macro- and micro elements and values of the main soil indicators for the studied profiles.

Horizon / Depth, cm	Rb	Sr	Cs	Ba	K	Na	Ca	Fe	Mn	pH / H ₂ O	CEC	Base- cation saturation, %	Total Carbon,	Carbonat es,	Physical clay,	
	mcg/g				weight %						cmol/ kg	% CEC	%	%	%	
Profile 3 Ekranic Spolic Technosols (Alcalic, Cambic, Chromic, Endoskeletal, Eutric, Toxic)																
Asp ₁	30-0	very black mass, agglomeration powder														
Aek	25-0	concrete flooring														
Asp _{2k}	0-50	255.08	370.06	11.58	7062.65	3.50	1.02	4.85	13.25	0.94	8.4	22.3	100	0.63	1.97	9.1
B ₁	50-105	279.53	215.64	15.44	1363.24	4.06	0.75	1.22	4.17	0.21	8	21.7	100	0.19	0.32	28.5
B _{2w}	105-170										7.5	20.6	100	0.11	0.25	40.5
1C	170-235	337.14	293.17	17.24	1577.58	5.51	1.41	1.41	3.00	0.12	7.6	20.9	100		0.17	22.7
2Cg	235-347	330.36	258.09	21.85	1559.41	4.50	0.96	2.31	4.65	0.19	8.2	26.3	100		0.54	50.6
Profile 6 Spolic Technosols (Alcalic, Chromic, Colluvic, Epicalcic, Eutric, Toxic)																
Asp ₁	30-0	granular and non-granular coke powder														
Asp _{2k}	0-40	137.26	230.51	9.08	6073.78	2.17	0.65	7.11	4.28	0.93	9.2	27.6	100	0.4	20.4	5.9
aC _f	40-60	194.57	100.70	13.07	1605.55	3.06	0.27	0.94	5.94	0.79	8	18.9	100		0	14.6
C _I	60-110										7	18.2	96.15		0	18.4
C _{II}	110-160	186.40	88.29	12.85	899.40	3.05	0.37	0.62	5.21	0.40	6.9	16.9	94.67		0	36
C _{III g}	160-260	193.86	113.99	14.07	1609.17	3.10	0.27	1.23	6.35	1.31	7.6	26.5	100		0.31	20.8
Profile 7 Spolic Technosols (Cambic, Chromic, Eutric, Gleyic, Toxic)																
Asp	10-0	coal dust														
Ak	0-38	167.49	199.35	10.58	4061.25	2.69	0.50	1.89	4.73	0.60	8	26.8	100	0.18	1.34	38.4
AB	38-68										7.3	22.5	96.89	0.09	0	47.9
Bw(g)	68-110	172.76	94.36	11.52	883.10	2.90	0.50	0.84	4.96	0.27	7.6	22	100		0	43.7
BC	110-165										7.9	22.6	100		0.94	33
C	165-210	174.40	94.39	10.86	916.03	3.03	0.36	0.83	4.58	0.27	7.7	20.5	100		1.64	20.4
Profile 8 Spolic Reductic Technosols (Chromic, Colluvic, Eutric, Gleyic, Toxic)																
Asp	20-0	tar, tar fus, naphthalene														
AC _{I g}	0-40	208.06	100.14	14.11	1144.15	3.05	0.43	1.09	5.36	0.34	7.9	19.3	100	0.14	0.31	22.7
AC _{II}	40-125										5.6	19.9	85.93	0.1	0.16	21.1
AC _{III}	125-225	182.06	80.71	12.42	1077.82	2.99	0.35	0.89	5.09	0.18	3.8	19.2	67.71	0.11	0	36.9
AC _{IV g}	225-400	167.94	122.21	10.95	817.01	2.38	0.43	1.26	4.91	0.22	6.6	24.3	93.02		0	55.7
Profile 11 Spolic Technosols (Chromic, Colluvic, Eutric, Skeletic)																
Asp ₁	20-0	loose sandy quartz substance														
Asp ₂	20-0	dark cast iron - slag														
Asp _{3k}	0-30	160.45	147.58	10.69	1875.23	2.31	0.40	4.17	5.26	0.41	8	25.7	100	0.23	1.74	38.4
AC _I	30-115	178.57	107.14	11.59	983.36	2.72	0.47	1.44	4.89	0.25	7.9	24.6	100	0.2	0.39	42.2
C _{II}	115-215	187.57	89.32	12.33	1080.52	3.12	0.40	1.38	5.82	0.29	7.2	24.1	94.61	0.13	0	19.1
Profile 13c Rhodic Eutric Cambisols (Clayic)																
A	0-32	168.03	109.89	11.18	862.71	2.61	0.53	1.39	3.72	0.09	7.8	33.1	100	0.81	0.39	60.8
AB	32-67										7.7	30.3	100	0.89	0.39	70.5
B _{1w}	67-116	189.79	132.33	12.15	963.35	2.61	0.50	1.27	3.88	0.10	7.8	32.5	100	0.63	0.46	73.7
B _{2w}	116-151										7.8	33	100	0.66	0.39	67.4
B ₃	151-185										7.8	35.1	100	0.92	4.2	70.5
BCK	185-220	250.65	173.18	15.85	1120.72	2.88	0.42	3.70	4.04	0.07	8	31.4	100	0.28	6.44	55.7
C	220-260										8	31.8	100	0.3	0.74	49.8

Table 2: Average contents of the studied elements, compared to reference values (Kabata-Pendias, 2011; Dyulgerov, 2005), distributed by geographical area and by technological pollution.

	Average in this study	Mediana	Max	Min		Field group I	Field group II	Field group III		Control profile 13c, average	Technosols, average	Average in Buhovo-Seslavtsi magmatic rocks	Average in soils, ref. data
	mcg/g												
Rb	206.1	186.98	337.14	137.26		300.53	178.48	175.53		202.82	206.68	341.3	68
Sr	156.05	118.1	370.06	80.71		284.24	122.46	114.68		138.47	159.16	591	175
Ba	1876.8	1132.43	7062.65	817.01		2890.72	1908.73	1313.04		982.26	2034.66	1715.7	460
Cs	12.97	12.24	21.85	9.08		16.53	11.95	11.54		13.06	12.95	16.095	5.06
Pb	174.04	174.39	698.02	41.78		228.54	191.51	174.14		43.05	197.16		27

Figure 2. Distribution of Rubidium, Strontium, Cesium, Barium and some important elements in the studied soil profiles

In this profile, the content of fine sand, in the composition of which the mentioned metals are also found, is mostly in the form of isomorphic inclusions in the primary rock-forming alkali feldspars and plagioclase of the source igneous rocks for the proluvial material (Stefanova, 2005, Kostov, 1993) (Table 3, Figure 3). This conclusion is also based on our previous mineralogical studies, according to which this profile has the maximum content of the indicated rock-forming minerals, and their amount even exceeds that of quartz in the soil-forming and surface horizons (Stoykova et al., 2021). On the other hand, Barium (Ba) in the studied soils has no significant correlation with the mentioned pedogenic and trace elements from the primary geochemical association. Barium has the highest excess in the studied soils, four times compared to the accepted reference norm (Kabata-Pendias, 2011), and this natural anomalous content is due, apart from the presence of the mentioned potassic-alkaline igneous rocks, also to its high contents in the Buhovo uranium deposit and the Kremikov barite-iron deposit (Kalaydjiev, 2009, Damianov, 1995). In this sense, the whole area can be considered as a territory with a naturally elevated Barium geochemical background.

According to the obtained results, the metal shows a bond with another group of elements forming a secondary technogenic association in the polluted region. A statistically significant positive correlation was determined between Barium and lead ($r=0.75$), based entirely on the man-made impact, in which part of the lead accumulated by air or mechanically is adsorbed by secondary sulfates and carbonates of the alkaline earth metals and especially Barium. Barium sulfate (Barite/ $BaSO_4$) is one of the least soluble Barium compounds (Orlov, 2005; Kabata Pendias, 2011), and according to Courtin-Nomade et al. (2008) it strongly adsorbs lead. The significant dependence of both elements on manganese and iron - $r_{Pb-Mn}=0.64$, $r_{Ba-Mn}=0.63$, $r_{Pb-Fe}=0.95$ and $r_{Ba-Fe}=0.61$, allows us to assume that part of Barium and lead are also adsorbed in the grids of secondary iron-manganese oxides (Table 4). The indicated significant relationships between Barium, lead, iron and manganese are the basis of the technogenic geochemical association,

secondarily generated by the activity of the combine. It includes Ca, S, Mn, Fe, Pb, Ba, Sr, Ag, In, Cu, Au, Te, Zn, Mo, Sb, Co, etc. (Stoykova, 2021). In Figure 3, the maximum values for the concentration coefficients of some of these elements can be traced, attesting to a very large accumulation in the surface spolic horizons of the studied Technosols. The maximum values for Barium were determined in the carbonate spolic horizons contaminated with agglomeration dust (in $\mu\text{g/g}$) - 7062.65 (Profile 3), with coke granules and dust - 6073.78 (Profile 6) and with coal dust - 4061.25 (Profile 7) (Table 1, Figure 2).

Strontium (Sr), which is isovalent with Barium and Calcium, has been significantly affected by the technogenesis that has taken place over the years. Despite the observed secondary concentration, Strontium is the only one among the four metals whose average content (156.05 $\mu\text{g/g}$) does not exceed the reference value (Kabata-Pendias, 2011), and it is also nearly four times lower than that presented by Dyulgerov (2005) value (591 $\mu\text{g/g}$) for its content in the source potassium-alkaline igneous rocks (Table 2). According to the indicators reported in this study, the maximum accumulation of Strontium is in the profiles contaminated with coal dust (Technosols, cambic/Profile 7) and coke dust and coke granules (Technosols, alkaline, colluvic/ Profile 6).

Among the four discussed metals, in their pedogenic geochemical interactions in the studied soils, Sr occupies an intermediate position between the two extreme groups - the alkali metals Rb and Cs on the one hand and the alkaline earth Ba on the other. Strontium exhibits a significant association with typomorphic elements from the primary association K, Na, Th, etc., but also with typomorphic elements from the secondary geochemical association - Ca and S. The indicators for CC of the alkaline earth metal are also positive, but below the limit of significance Fe, Mn and Pb (Table 4). Another observation on Sr indicators, which otherwise reflects its intermediate position, reports that it alone has a statistically significant association with the two main salt-forming macroelements, P and S, with Rb and Cs bound to P (as part of the primary magmatogenic association), and Ba with S (as part of the secondary technogenic association). The interstitial position of Strontium is energetically determined by its atomic structure, according to which it is more advantageous to replace Na^+ , rather than its isovalent Ca^{2+} , in the structure of primary plagioclases. This allows during the weathering stage, due to a greater energy mismatch, to more easily free itself from its positions in the crystal lattice and take its own geochemical path in exogenous conditions (Fersman, 1953, Stefanova, 2005), where also its alkaline earth properties. In the studied soils, this is expressed in interaction with S and accumulation of Strontium as sulfate (Celestine / SrSO_4) - in independent phases or as part of solid solutions with other sulfates, mainly calcium (Gypsum, Anhydrite) and Barium (Barite). Thus, the contamination of the site of the plant has contributed to a very large accumulation of heavy alkaline earth metals in all the alkalized spolic/carbonate surface horizons of the Technosols, where they, by virtue of their references in the soil and according to the numerical data obtained by us, are present as carbonates with mixed composition associated with them hardly soluble sulfates and phases adsorbed by iron and manganese oxides (Kabata-Pendias, 2011, Burger et al., 2019) (Table 3, Figure 3).

The heavy alkali metals Rb and Cs, in accordance with the trend of their pedogenic counterpart potassium, in the contaminated carbonate spolic horizons migrate downwards along the soil profile. Conversely, sodium, despite its significant correlations with the two heavy alkali metals, is concentrated in these horizons. According to their physicochemical properties, these are the most alkaline horizons, with alkaline degradation reported in places (Stoykova and Teoharov, 2020) and with minimal clay content (Table 1, Table 3).

Table 3. Concentration coefficients (CC) of the investigated elements, calculated as the ratio between the values in each of the horizons to the values in the lowest horizon of the profile

CC	K	Na	Ca	Mn	Fe	P	S	Rb	Sr	Cs	Ba
Profile 3											
Asp2	0.78	1.06	2.10	4.89	2.96	0.63	1.46	0.77	1.43	0.53	4.53
B I	0.90	0.78	0.53	1.05	0.93	0.49	0.97	0.85	0.84	0.71	0.87
K	1.23	1.46	0.61	0.63	0.69	0.75	0.64	1.02	1.14	0.79	1.01
2C g	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Profile 6											
Asp2	0.70	2.44	5.78	0.84	0.67	0.61	1.00	0.71	2.02	0.65	3.77
aCf	0.99	1.00	0.77	0.27	0.91	0.86	0.59	1.00	0.88	0.93	1.00
C II	0.98	1.39	0.51	0.29	0.77	0.79	0.64	0.96	0.77	0.91	0.56
C III g	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Profile 7											
Ak	0.89	1.39	2.28	2.50	1.01	0.94	1.48	0.96	2.11	0.97	4.43
Bw(g)	0.96	1.37	1.02	1.25	1.02	1.11	0.66	0.99	1.00	1.06	0.96
C	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Profile 8											
AC I g	1.28	1.00	0.86	1.42	1.00	1.25	1.81	1.24	0.82	1.29	1.40
AC III	1.25	0.81	0.71	0.84	0.97	0.99	0.98	1.08	0.66	1.13	1.32
AC IV	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Profile 11											
Asp3	0.74	1.00	3.02	1.26	0.81	0.72	1.46	0.86	1.65	0.87	1.74
AC I	0.87	1.17	1.05	0.85	0.83	0.70	1.19	0.95	1.20	0.94	0.91
C II	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Profile 13c											
A	0.91	1.26	0.38	1.50	1.09	1.17	0.49	0.67	0.63	0.71	0.77
Bw	0.90	1.19	0.34	1.67	1.07	1.31	0.91	0.76	0.76	0.77	0.86
BC	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1

Exceptions to the considered trends are observed in two of the profiles - in the control uncontaminated profile of Rhodic Cambisol (Profile 13c) and in Reductic Technosols (Profile 8).

Periodically reducing conditions throughout the depth and strong acidification in the intermediate horizons/layers of Reductic Technosols have predetermined a similar behavior of the four metals - their relative maximum concentration in the surface ogleic horizon. In these conditions, they are associated with a number of pedogenic and trace elements, all influenced by a strong acid effect (pH 3.8), partial periodic water upward migration and accumulation when the thermodynamic conditions change in the surface environment of the soil profile, which can be considered as alkaline -oxidative geochemical barrier with pH 7.9. These elements are K, Mn, S, P, Fe²⁺, Mg, Pb, As, Te, Mo, etc. (Table 1, Table 3, Figure 3; Stoykova, 2021). According to the geochemical profile of the association and in accordance with the empirical data on the mineral composition of this horizon, the maximum content of smectite is there for the entire profile, the presence of iron sulfide (Pyrite/FeS₂) is also determined, only for the entire study (Stoykova and Teoharov, 2021), and its similarity indirectly suggests the presence of a number of other heavy and transition metal sulfides. According to the morphological field studies, the horizon is highly manganized, which also determines the presence of iron and manganese oxides, from which specifically Ba has a pronounced tendency to be adsorbed (Kabata-Pendias, 2011).

In the uncontaminated Rhodic Cambisol, the behavior of the four considered metals is also similar - all migrate downward and concentrate in the BCK carbonate horizon (Table 1, Table 3,

Figure 3. Bar charts of the Concentration coefficients (CC) of Rb, Sr, Cs, Ba and some important elements in this study

Figure 3). Illite and calcite contents were determined in this horizon (Stoykova and Teoharov, 2021), which suggests that, in addition to being isomorphically included in primary feldspars and plagioclase, the discussed metals are also present in such a form - replacing potassium in secondary hydromicas or as carbonates. In sulfate form they can also be present, since sulfur also has maximum values for the profile in this horizon. The question of the influence of the soil microbiome is debatable, since only in this profile is it preserved relatively authentic. In the microbiological study of Technosols, not enough living organisms were found to carry out the experiments, and in this sense the technogenic changes recorded in these soils took place to some extent in an abiotic environment.

Table 4. Correlation coefficients (r) between Rubidium, Strontium, Cesium and Barium and reference elements in the studied soils.

	K	Na	Ca	Fe	Mn	S	P	Rb	Cs	Ba	Sr	Pb	Th ²³²	U ²³⁸
K	1.00													
Na	0.78	1.00												
Ca	-0.22	0.27	1.00											
Fe	-0.03	0.11	0.30	1.00										
Mn	-0.18	-0.13	0.38	0.56	1.00									
S	0.04	0.19	0.53	0.48	0.70	1.00								
P	0.83	0.70	-0.03	0.21	0.08	0.24	1.00							
Rb	0.92	0.77	-0.05	0.04	-0.23	0.13	0.81	1.00						
Cs	0.79	0.48	-0.20	-0.17	-0.26	0.02	0.78	0.88	1.00					
Ba	-0.07	0.37	0.78	0.61	0.63	0.75	0.13	-0.02	-0.28	1.00				
Sr	0.53	0.86	0.59	0.39	0.20	0.58	0.59	0.64	0.33	0.71	1.00			
Pb	-0.09	0.11	0.39	0.95	0.64	0.58	0.11	-0.09	-0.33	0.75	0.41	1.00		
Th ²³²	0.85	0.87	0.09	0.04	-0.24	0.13	0.86	0.94	0.81	0.11	0.74	-0.07	1.00	
U ²³⁸	0.44	0.10	-0.19	0.18	0.50	0.33	0.56	0.29	0.37	0.08	0.10	0.21	0.20	1.00
coarse and medium sand	0.15	0.01	0.23	0.29	0.57	0.45	0.13	0.01	-0.09	0.41	0.17	0.43	-0.12	0.44
fine sand	0.61	0.64	-0.09	-0.40	-0.28	-0.18	0.46	0.44	0.36	-0.06	0.31	-0.32	0.52	0.30
silt	-0.06	-0.17	-0.38	-0.36	-0.49	-0.30	-0.03	0.05	0.28	-0.50	-0.27	-0.48	0.10	-0.12
clay	-0.28	-0.16	-0.26	-0.42	-0.63	-0.48	-0.32	-0.12	-0.02	-0.49	-0.27	-0.56	-0.02	-0.61

The observation of a general trend of the four metals in the uncontaminated soil allows to draw a general conclusion, according to which the concentration of heavy alkaline earth metals Ba and Sr in the surface soil horizons can be considered as a sign of irreversible or difficult to reverse soil degradation accompanied by alkalization and reduction of clay substance.

Conclusion

The content of heavy alkali (Rb and Cs) and alkaline earth metals (Ba and Sr) in the studied soils is geochemically inherited from the initial high contents of the elements in the soil-forming proluvial rocks, with the highest degree of Strontium removal, and the highest the degree of Barium accumulation.

In the process of natural pedogenesis, within the uncontaminated Rhodic Cambisol, the four metals exhibit similar properties - downward migration and accumulation in the transitional carbonate BCK horizon (185 - 220 cm). Similar properties also occur as a result of strong acidification in the intermediate soil horizons and periodically reducing conditions along the entire soil profile, during which they are concentrated in the surface oligaceous horizon of the soil in the composition of secondary smectites, iron and manganese oxides, sulfates and carbonates.

It has been determined that the long-term active technogenesis on the territory of the former "Kremikovtsi" metallurgical plant has influenced such that the alkaline earth metals Ba and Sr have very high contents in soil profiles contaminated with agglomeration dust, coke and coal products. There they are concentrated in the surface carbonate spolic horizons and are also present as mixed-

composition carbonates, their associated sparingly soluble sulfates, and phases adsorbed by iron and manganese oxides. A statistically significant correlation between Ba and Pb was determined, which is attributed to the secondary technogenic accumulation of both metals in the contaminated surface horizons and to the marked adsorption of lead by the practically insoluble Barium sulfate.

These observations allow considering the concentration of heavy alkaline earth metals in surface soil horizons as a sign of irreversible or difficult to reverse soil degradation, accompanied by alkalization of the environment, reduction of clay substance and secondary Lead enrichment.

References

- Angelov, V., Antonov M., Gerdjikov S. Petrov P., Tanatsiev S., Kiselinov H., Marinova R., Valev V. (2008). Geological map of Bulgaria M 1: 50000, m. pp. K-34-48-B (Elin Pelin). Research Institute of Geology and Geophysics JSC, MGU "St. Ivan Rilski", S. (In Bulgarian)
- Burger, A., Lichtscheidl, I. (2019). Strontium in the environment: Review about reactions of plants towards stable and radioactive Strontium isotopes. *Science of The Total Environment*, 653, 1458–1512. doi:10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.10.312
- Courtin-Nomade, A., Soubrand-Colin M., Marcus M.A., Fakra S.C. (2008). Evidence for the incorporation of Lead into Barite from Waste Rock Pile Materials. *Environmental Science and Technology*, 42, 8, 2867-2872.
- Damyantov, Zh. (1995). Mineral composition, zonation and genesis of the deposit. In: *Guide/Barite-iron ore deposit "Kremikovtsi" and the Jurassic system in the region of Kremikovtsi*. Publisher: University of Mining and Geology, Sofia, 15-22. (In Bulgarian)
- Dyulgerov, M. (2005). Potassium Alkaline Magmatism from Stara Planina, Bulgaria: Petrological study of Buhovo-Seslavtsi, Svidnia and Shipka plutons, Autoreph. Sofia University, University of Paris XI, Sofia, 35 p. (in Bulgarian)
- Faitondjiev, L., Stanislavova L., Thculdjian H., Georgiev B. (2000). Changes in soils of the Region of Kremikotzi. *Sofia, Soil Science Agrochemistry and Ecology*, № 4, 3-10.
- Fersman, A.E. (1953). Selected works, vol. II. M., USSR Academy of Sciences, 768 p. (in Russian)
- IUSS Working Group WRB. (2015). World Reference Base for Soil Resources 2014, update 2015, International soil classification system for naming soils and creating legends for soil maps. *World Soil Resources Reports No. 106*. FAO, Rome, 192 p.
- Jaritz M. 2004. Barium. In: *Elements and Their Compounds in the Environment*, 2 eds, E. Merian, M. Anke, M. Ihnat, M. Stoeppler, 627–634, Wiley-VCH, Weinheim.
- Kabata-Pendias A. (2011). Trace elements in soils and plants - 4th edition, Includes bibliographical references and index. CRC Press, NW, 534 p.
- Kalaydzhiiev, S. (1993). Structural control of uranium deposits in the area of the Iskar Gorge. – *Journal of Bulg. geol. Soc.* 54, 1, 13-20. (In Bulgarian)
- Kamenov, B. (2003). Magmatic petrology. University Publishing House of Sofia University "St. Kl. Ohridski", S., 872 p. (In Bulgarian)
- Kostov, I. (1993). Mineralogy. Technique, S., 734 p. (In Bulgarian)
- Naidenov, M., Travesi, A. (1977) Nondestructive neutron activation analysis of Bulgarian soils, *Soil Sci.*, 124/3: 152-160.
- Nakao A., Funakawa S., Kosaki T. (2003). Kinetics of Cs adsorption on soils with different mineralogical composition. *Proc. Int. Symp. Radioecol. Environ. Dosimetry*. 191–195, Rokkasho, Aomori, Japan.

Orlov, D.S., Sadovnikova L.K., Sukhanova N.I. (2005). Soil chemistry. M, Ed. "High School", 559 p. (In Russian)

Perelman A.I. (1989). Geochemistry. Higher School, Moscow, ISBN: 5-06-000472-4, 528 p. (In Russian)

Rollinson, H. (1993). Using geochemical data: evaluation, presentation, interpretation. – Longman, 392 pp.

Schulin, R., Keller A., Daskalova A., Mondeshka M., Dinev N., Koutev V., Todorova I. (2004). Geostatistical Soil Quality Assessment and Regional Mass Flux Analysis for Sustainable Land Use Planning and Management, Final report. Swiss National Science Foundation Scientific Co-operation between Eastern Europe and Switzerland SCOPES IP 062642, ETH Zurich, UACEG Sofia, ISSNP Sofia, EEA Sofia.

Stoykova, M. (2020). Alkalisiation of Technosols from the territory of the “Kremikovtzi” MW. “International seminar of Ecology – 2019” 18 - 19 April 2019. Institute of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research – Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Sofia, Bulgaria, Farrago, 6(1), 66-72.

Stoykova, M. (2021). Characteristics of soils with geochemical and technogenic loading, formed on old Quaternary sediments. Abstract of the Ph. D. Thesis, ISSAPP “N. Poushkarov”, 32 p. (In Bulgarian)

Stoykova, M., Teoharov M. (2021). Mineral composition of technogenic soils from the territory of the former metallurgical plant "Kremikovtzi". Proceedings of the National Committee "Ecology and Agrotechnology - Basic Science and Practical Implementation", Volume 2, ISSN 2683-0663, 373 - 379. (in Bulgarian)

Teoharov, M. et all. (2019). Genetic and applied classifications of soils and lands in Bulgaria. Bulgarian Soil Science Society, Sofia, Avangard, 212 p. (in Bulgarian)